

Study and Analysis of Digital Drug Addiction and Child

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Abstract-

This study aims to investigate digital game addiction among today's children of 8-16 years. The performance of children in all other areas of life has been seen to drop drastically due to this addiction. Various studies have found out conclusively that how children develop aggressive behavior due to digital game addiction. Their grades in school have also been found to drop. The study in Kirsehir province took part in the study of complete sampling. The study used a 14-item online games addiction scale developed by the researchers. Reputation frequency function analysis and chi-square test were used for data analysis. Researchers argue that multiple factors contribute to this addiction, the first and foremost being the easy and cheap availability of electronic gadgets and the digitization of education. Besides that, in this fast-paced capitalist society, parents are unable to spend time with children leading to neglect and loneliness in the child. Studies also show that children suffering from gaming syndrome are unable to grow up emotionally, developing impulsive behaviours. The study aims to analyse how the problem can be tackled while also understanding that electronic gadgets are an indispensable part of our lives too.

Keywords: *Drugs, Video games, Disorder, Addiction*

I. Introduction

A drug-related offense is the possessing, manufacturing, sale or distributing of drugs, which have been recognized to have the potential to be abused, such as cocaine, heroin, morphine and amphetamine. Both the manufacturing and trafficking of drugs are considered as crime. Such crimes at the bigger level are committed and controlled by organized gangs and cartels.

The act came into force on 14 November 1985 as THE NARCOTIC DRUGS AND PSYCHOTROPIC SUBSTANCES ACT 1985 (shortened to NDPS Act). Under the NDPS ACT, it is illegal for a person to produce/manufacture/cultivate, possess, sell, purchase, transport, store, and/or consume any narcotic drug or psychotropic, In addition, the Central Government

added Chapter IIIA to regulate these devices' registration. The Central Drugs Standard Control Organization has created a specific online portal to register the medical devices says in sub-rule (1) of Rule 19 A with the Central Licensing Authority. After the beginning of this chapter, registration will be required for a period of eighteen months. After that, registration will be voluntary.

II. Literature Review

According to the Sanjay Kumar Report of India, says in that more than 40 000 men and boys (ages 12 to 60) were questioned for the national household survey, while ancillary studies focused on drug abuse in rural communities, border regions, jail prisoners, and women. In India, the most often abused drugs are alcohol, cannabis, opium, and heroin. The most popular drugs for injection are buprenorphine, propoxyphene, and heroin. The poll found that, in India, which has a population of little over a billion people, 62.5 million individuals use alcohol, 8.75 million people use cannabis, two million people use opiates, and 0.6 million people use sedatives or hypnotics. According to the survey, between 17% and 26% of these individuals fit the description of dependent users who require immediate treatment. Only approximately one in six persons who consume alcohol are likely to seek treatment, compared to roughly 25% of opiate and cannabis users. Gary Lewis, the South Asia regional representative of the UN Office on Drugs and Crime, had rightly said that the problem of drugs is no more a problem exclusive to urban life as drug abuse has become a common phenomenon everywhere.

Research Question

- Can society break this connection with the help of the laws?
- Why do only some people get addicted to drugs?

Research Objective

The goal of this study is to evaluate that Drug abuse is a crime in our country, and not only adults but also children are falling prey to it. Making drugs is not only a crime, buying them, but making people and children addicted to them is also a crime. Drugs have been successful in inculcating the children of this generation and making them hollow from the inside.

1. The effect of drugs (physical, psychological, financial) on the person abusing them and also on abuser's family and peers.

2. Drug usage, particularly tobacco smoking, has a tremendous impact on society and chronic illness outcomes in terms of public health.
3. Effect on society at large, as drug abuse leads to increased crime and violence;
4. Drug abuse is also an economic burden on the country since the public expenditure on healthcare increases. Also, the population involved in drug abuse becomes low on productivity, contributing very little to the country's wealth.

III. Research Methodology

The researcher has followed doctrinal methodology of research. The researcher has relied on secondary sources of data. A number of books, articles, news reports, websites, journals and legal statutes have been referred.

Drugs

Abusing drugs or other substances is the usage of certain compounds to provide the brain pleasure sensations. In addition to the long-term health effects of drug misuse, drug users who use needles run the danger of developing hepatitis B and C, HIV, and hepatitis B and C. Drug use's root causes. What causes drug abuse has been a question of study since long. A variety of factors seem to cause people to start taking drugs and then abuse them.

Particularly among young individuals and students in schools, curiosity and peer pressure prescription drug use that was initially intended to treat pain may have evolved into addictive behaviour and become recreational. Chemicals may be utilised in religious ceremonies or practises. recreation as a source of inspiration for creative endeavours.

Drug categories;-

Drugs abuse falls into three groups and these include:

Depressants: Examples of this are heroin and sleeping medications (barbiturates), which suppress the brain's capacities.

Stimulants: These stimulate the brain, resulting in higher activity bursts and alertness. Additionally possible side effects include a quickening heartbeat, dilated pupils, increased blood pressure, nausea or vomiting, behavioural changes like agitation, and poor judgement. With the use of cocaine and amphetamines, delusional psychosis may arise in extreme cases.

Hallucinogens create dissociative experiences that feel "out of this world" and induce hallucinations. Incorrect sensory perception, hallucination, paranoia, and even sadness can all be brought on by hallucinogens. Ecstasy, mescaline, and LSD are some instances.

Can society break this connection with the help of the laws?

Our society holds various taboos, some of which are dubious while others may have a long history and need not be repeated. The use of drugs is one of the taboos that were discussed. India is a nation where people have consumed the most drugs of all kinds because of their rebellious nature. But why? Is it because it violates the law? Or is it because it is harmful to those who consume it? Regardless of the cause, this rebellious attitude unquestionably has consequences that society faces today. Abusing drugs or other substances is the usage of certain compounds to provide the brain pleasure sensations. According to an estimate, there are about 200 million drug users in the world. What is alarming is that the rate of increase in drug users is increasing exponentially.

Drug abuse and crime are a long-standing phenomenon and a vicious cycle that India is no exception. This cycle has a negative connotation as one of India's most severe social issues due to the widespread use of drugs in the country. Alcohol, cannabis, and other forms of substance abuse are common in society and a friend to many in the country.

Why do only some people get addicted to drugs?

Addiction to drugs and alcohol is a complicated brain disease that can last a lifetime. Medication and therapy can be used to manage and treat addiction, but relapse is always possible. Addiction is often viewed with suspicion; there is a widespread misperception that abstaining from alcohol or drugs is a choice that is upheld by a lack of morals. Abuse of alcohol or drugs as a means of coping with various stressors raises the likelihood of addiction.

Abuse-related neurological changes, excessive stress, and withdrawal symptoms all make quitting difficult. It is unfair to attribute people's desire to stop to willpower. Numerous studies demonstrate that several factors initiate and sustain addiction, requiring professional assistance to remain sober.

Those who suffer from a substance use disorder seek assistance from mental health professionals or spend time in a rehabilitation facility with regular follow-up visits. The intensity, history of alcohol or substance abuse, substance(s) used, and co-morbidities all

influence the treatment plan, whether it is residential or outpatient. After a professional evaluation, treatment consists of behavioral therapy and medication. It also includes taking care of health issues. For instance, individuals who have a severe addiction frequently experience withdrawal symptoms that require proper management or can result in seizures or other health complications.

Laws:-

The penalty for violating Section 15 of the NDPS Act will be determined by the quantity of the prohibited substance.

1. if the violation involves a small quantity (less than 1 kilogram), severe imprisonment for up to six months, a fine of up to 10,000 yen, or both;
2. when the violation involves more than a small quantity but less than the commercial quantity, severe imprisonment for a period of up to ten years and a fine of up to 1 lac rupees;
3. If the offense involves commercial quantities, the penalty is severe imprisonment for a period of not less than ten years but up to twenty years, as well as a fine of not less than 1 lac but up to 2 lac rupees.

Section 276 of the Indian Penal Code states that anyone who knowingly sells, offers, or exposes for sale, or issues from a dispensary for medicinal purposes, any drug or medical preparation, as a different drug or medical preparation, will be punished with either six months in prison or a fine of one thousand rupees, or both.

Section 10 of the NDPS gives the state government the authority to allow, regulate, and control-

(1) The State Government may, subject to section 8, by rules: a) allow and regulate the possession, transportation, interstate import and export, warehousing, purchase, consumption, and use of poppy straw;

ii) the possession, transportation, import, export, sale, purchase, consumption, and use of opium across states;

(iii) the cultivation of any cannabis plant, as well as its production, manufacture, possession, transportation, import from one state to another, export from one state to another, sale, purchase, use, or consumption (chars excluded);

(iv) the production of medicinal opium or any preparation containing manufactured drugs using materials that the manufacturer is authorized to possess under the law;

(v) the possession, transportation, purchase, sale, use, or consumption of manufactured drugs other than prepared opium and coca leaf, as well as any preparation containing manufactured drugs; and (vii) the import and export of manufactured drugs between states.

Judicial point of view

The stance of the judicial system towards drug abusers has been practical over the years. It would appear that some judges were motivated to do this because they believed that the courts were uniquely positioned to achieve the best possible outcomes for these people. Various surveys and studies favour this approach, especially for repeat offenders of drug abuse and those who has stopped responding to the rehabilitation techniques. This article examines this research evidence and its implications for the creation of drug-abusing criminal policies and programs that are both cost-effective and effective.

The papers also takes notice of the rise of drug overdose cases in Australia, the rise of illegal drug markets, rising violence and crime rates and the need to establish special courts for such cases. The paper then discusses how state politicians adapted and adopted the drug treatment court model from the United States in their efforts to deal with drug-related criminals.

Changes in the rules

The Indian pharmaceutical industry's regulatory issues are examined and evaluated in this article. Now since we have come a long way when it comes to drug abuse and the legal jurisprudence on drugs has evolved worldwide as well as in India, having an understanding of the regulatory procedure in this sector is of the utmost importance.

Over the past few decades, the Drugs and Cosmetics Act of 1940 and the Rules of 1945 have undergone numerous revisions. Several changes were made to the Drugs and Cosmetics Rules in 2020.

If prescriptions are to be sent via email, the licensee must register with the licensing authority using an email address.

Patients who live in the same revenue district as the licensee must receive their medications at their doorstep.

In acute conditions, the prescription must be presented to the licensee within seven days of its issue, while in chronic diseases, the prescription must be presented to the licensee within 30 days.

Rule 65(17) of the Drugs and Cosmetics Rules, 1945 prohibits not only the selling but also the stocking of such a drug which has reached its date of expiry as to its potency; which is mentioned on the label or wrapper or container of the drug.

The Central Government has amended Rule 2 of the Drugs and Cosmetics Rules, 1945 to include the term "marketer" in clause (a), establishing the marketer's responsibility for quality and regulatory compliance.

The effective date of this amendment is March 1, 2021. However, the amendment does not contain any specific procedures or guidelines for a marketing company to follow to preserve the drugs' quality. Until now, pharmaceutical companies have been marketing drugs under a contract manufacturing agreement in which manufacturers are responsible for drug quality and regulatory compliance. The pharmaceuticals are being sold or distributed by marketing firms under a wholesale license with storage conditions. Marketers could plead guilty under Section 19 of the Drugs and Cosmetics Act of 1940 if the drugs were obtained from a licensed manufacturer, and marketing companies were made co-accused in cases of Not of Standard Quality.

Declared as a "Drug" by the Central Government, the following medical devices are intended for use in animals or humans. Any device intended by its manufacturer to be used specifically for humans or animals but which may assist in its intended function by such means for one or more of the specific purposes of (i) diagnosis, prevention, monitoring, treatment, or alleviation of any disease or disorder; (ii) material or another article, whether used alone or in combination, including software or accessories) any injury or disability diagnosis, monitoring, treatment, relief, or assistance; (iii) investigation, replacement, modification, or support of a physiological process or anatomical structure; (iv) sustaining life or supporting it; v) medical device disinfection; and (vi) the power to control conception.

IV. Suggestion And Conclusion

The use of drugs can be harmful to both the user's and the public's health. The goal of the government is to stop people from using drugs. Addiction treatment is available if a person develops an addiction. Preventative measures are in place for those who cannot kick their habit.

Bad and insidious diseases like drug addiction should be rid of our future generations and generations to come. Many laws existing in our country should be made stricter and all kinds of drugs should be banned with the help of their laws.

Abuse of drugs affects all aspects of life; family life, community, and overall health and well-being. The effects can't stop because there are so many different drugs. Drug abuse has no one-size-fits-all or discriminatory effect. Any region of the world is susceptible to drug abuse, which can have devastating consequences for all parties involved.

A person's overall health and well-being can be negatively impacted if they choose to use any kind of illegal drug or abuse medicines that have been prescribed to them. Addicts' overall health and wellness can be negatively impacted in the short and long term by this. Depending on the kind of drug that is being abused, there may be numerous short-term effects. Some medications can make your heart rate faster, cause you to hallucinate, and even make you very dehydrated. Addiction can have far-reaching effects. Drug abuse can result in stroke, cancer, HIV/AIDS, liver disease, and cardiovascular disease. Some of these effects occur when drugs are taken for an extended period or in high doses; nevertheless, some may occur after only one use. A person suffering from addiction may go through a number of mental health problems that might severely harm their own life. More often than men, substance-abusing women experience negative self-perceptions.

It cannot be denied that the situation of an addict affects not only him but also his family environment. When an addict lives at home, a family may face several challenges. Many different kinds of abuse can occur in a home.